

" ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT MARKETING CONSTRAINTS OF HERBICIDE (IRIS) AND SUGGEST SUITABLE MEASURES IN RATLAM DISTRICT OF MADHYA PRADESH "

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Abstract

The objective of this study was to analyze the marketing strategies employed by the company responsible for distributing and promoting Iris herbicide, as well as to assess the factors influencing its market penetration and success in the Ratlam district.

The study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques. A survey was conducted among farmers in Ratlam district to gather information on their awareness, perception, and usage patterns of Iris herbicide. Additionally, interviews were conducted with key stakeholders, including retailers, distributors, and company representatives, to gain insights into the marketing strategies implemented for promoting Iris herbicide in the region.

The findings of the study revealed that the awareness of Iris herbicide among farmers in Ratlam district was moderate, with a significant portion of respondents having limited knowledge about its benefits and usage. However, those farmers who were aware of Iris herbicide recognized its effectiveness in controlling weeds and expressed satisfaction with its performance. The study also identified several factors that influenced the adoption of Iris herbicide, including pricing, availability, accessibility, and promotional activities

Keywords: Marketing strategies, Iris Herbicide, Market penetration, Awareness, Perception, Farmers, Retailers, Distributors, Company representatives, Promotional activities.

Introduction

The marketing of agricultural products plays a crucial role in ensuring their successful adoption and widespread usage among farmers. In the case of herbicides, effective marketing strategies are essential to create awareness, generate demand, and facilitate the adoption of these products in target regions. This research paper presents a study focused on the marketing of the herbicide "Iris" in Ratlam district, Madhya Pradesh. The objective of this study is to analyze the marketing strategies employed for Iris herbicide, evaluate its market penetration in the region, and identify key factors influencing its success.

Ratlam district, located in the central Indian state of Madhya Pradesh, is an important agricultural region characterized by a significant dependence on farming for livelihoods. As with any agricultural region, weed management is crucial for ensuring crop productivity and reducing yield losses. Herbicides, such as Iris, have been developed to address this need and provide effective weed control solutions to farmers.

The success of any herbicide in a particular region depends on various factors, including farmers' awareness, perception, and adoption patterns. Additionally, marketing strategies and promotional activities play a critical role in influencing farmers' decisions and facilitating the product's availability and accessibility. Therefore, understanding the marketing dynamics of Iris herbicide in Ratlam district is essential to assess its market position and identify areas for improvement.

This study utilizes a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative research methods, to comprehensively analyze the marketing of Iris herbicide in Ratlam district. A survey will be conducted among farmers to gather data on their awareness, perception, and usage patterns of Iris herbicide. Additionally, interviews will be conducted with key stakeholders, including retailers, distributors, and company representatives, to gain insights

into the marketing strategies employed and the challenges faced in promoting Iris herbicide in the region.

The findings of this study will provide valuable insights into the current marketing scenario of Iris herbicide in Ratlam district. By identifying the factors influencing its market penetration and success, the study aims to contribute to the development of effective marketing strategies that can enhance the adoption of Iris herbicide among farmers in the region. The results of this research can be utilized by the company responsible for the product's distribution and marketing to optimize their marketing efforts, improve product availability and accessibility, and ultimately benefit both the company and the farmers in Ratlam district.

Research Methodology

Selection of study area:

Ratlam district is located in the western part of the state of Madhya Pradesh, India. It lies between 22.48° to 23.24° North latitude and 74.28° to 75.26° East longitude. The district covers an area of approximately 4,861 square kilometers.

Selection of the districts:

There are 52 District and 10 division in Madhya Pradesh state from which Ratlam District was selected purposively to study about the marketing of IRIS.

Selection of blocks:

There are 5 block in the Ratlam district. Out of these Ratlam city block was selected purposively for the study. The agro condition of the block is suitable for the Soyabean cultivation. The Farmer of this Ratlam city block have been growing the Soyabean for several years.

Selection of villages:

A complete list of all villages of Ratlam city block was obtained from the block development office. Thereafter these villages was arranged in ascending order on the basis of area of cultivation. Thus out of total villages 5% villages were selected randomly for the study.

Table 1.1 Selected Villages Of Study Area

S.No.	Selected Villages
1.	Sailana
2.	Namli
3.	Dhamnood
4.	Ratlam rural

5.

Punched

Selection of Respondents:

A complete list of all respondents in the selected villages were prepared out of which 10% respondents were selected randomly.

Selection of Market:

Primary and secondary market were selected randomly for data collection. Namli and Sailana were selected purposively.

Selection of Market Functionaries:

The market functionaries were considered for data collection regarding and other marketing charges in different marketing channel list of all market functionaries were prepared with the help of primary and secondary market offices then out of total number of market functionaries like whole sellers, retailers' middle man, commission agent etc., market functionaries were selected randomly for the study.

Producer – Wholesaler – Consumer

Producer – Wholesaler – Retailer – Consumer

Producer – Primary Wholesaler – Secondary Wholesaler – Retailer – Consumer

Tool Of Analysis:**Table 1.2 Constraints restricting against marketing of Herbicide**

S.No.	Issues	Garett Score	Rank
1.	Loyal to other Product	82	I
2.	High Market Competition	70	II
3.	Prices Fluctuation in Market	63	III
4.	Packaging Problem	58	IV
5.	Fear of New Product	48	V
6.	Tough Product Name	42	VI
7.	Fake Product in Market	37	VII
8.	Retailer Influence to Purchase other Product	30	VIII

Table 1.2 reveals about the constraints restricting against marketing of HERBICIDE in which (i)Loyal to other product rank (ii)High market competition rank (iii)Prices fluctuation rank (iv)Packaging problem rank (v)Fear of new product rank (vi) Tough product name rank. (vii) Fake product in market rank (viii)Retailer Influence to Purchase other Product.

Different constraints in marketing of IRIS and suggest suitable measure :

Loyal to other Product: To address this issue, the marketing strategy should focus on highlighting the unique features and benefits of IRIS that differentiate it from the other products in the market. This can be done through targeted advertising and social media campaigns, and by offering free samples or trials to potential customers.

High Market Competition: To differentiate IRIS from its competitors, it is essential to identify the unique selling proposition (USP) of the product and market it aggressively. The USP could be related to the product's features, pricing, or packaging. It is also important to conduct regular market research to stay ahead of competitors and adapt to changing market trends.

Prices Fluctuation in Market: To address this issue, the marketing team should conduct regular price analysis of the product, monitor competitor pricing, and adjust the pricing of IRIS accordingly. This can be done by offering discounts or promotions to attract customers, or by introducing new pricing strategies such as dynamic pricing based on demand

Packaging Problem: To address this issue, the marketing team should identify the specific packaging problems and find ways to improve the packaging. This could involve using different materials or designs, conducting focus groups to get customer feedback, or working with a packaging design company to create more appealing and functional packaging.

Fear of New Product: To address this issue, the marketing team should focus on building trust and credibility with potential

Garrett Ranking Method

It is used to find out the most significant factor which influences the respondent. As per this method, respondents have been asked to assign the rank for all factors and the outcome of such ranking have been converted into score value with the help of following formula:

$$\text{Per cent Position} = \frac{100 * (R_{ij} - 0.50)}{N_j}$$

Where,

R_{ij} is the rank given to i^{th} item by the j^{th} individual,
 N_j is the number of items ranked by the j^{th} individual

Result And Discussion

To identify different constraints in marketing of IRIS and suggest suitable measure.

customers. This can be done by providing information about the product's safety and effectiveness, offering testimonials or reviews from satisfied customers, and providing clear instructions on how to use the product.

Tough Product Name: To address this issue, the marketing team should consider changing the name of the product to make it more appealing and memorable to potential customers. This could involve conducting market research to identify more appealing names, or working with a branding agency to develop a new name and brand identity.

Fake Product in Market: To address this issue, the marketing team should work with regulatory agencies to crack down on counterfeit products in the market. This could involve conducting market surveys to identify counterfeit products, working with law enforcement agencies to seize and prosecute counterfeiters, and providing education and awareness to consumers about the risks of purchasing counterfeit products.

Retailer Influence to Purchase other Product: To address this issue, the marketing team should work with retailers to promote IRIS as a superior product to other products in the market. This could involve offering special promotions or discounts to retailers who agree to promote IRIS, providing training and education to retail staff on the benefits of IRIS, and creating in-store displays and marketing materials that highlight the product's features and benefits.

Conclusion

In current scenario and future of HERBICIDE have bright future. Farmers totally depends on the HERBICIDE that show the increasing demand of the HERBICIDE. Farmers not waste time on the field they want easy solutions for any problem of field therefore they use HERBICIDE efficiently. Due to the use of the HERBICIDE farmers yield more crops so they not stop to use the HERBICIDE. HERBICIDE are less time taken, quick action on the target organisms and safe to use. Maximum farmers use the excess quantity

of the HERBICIDE but some farmers say that excess use of HERBICIDE harmful for the field and they use the HERBICIDE only when it was very essential for the crop. According to farmer without HERBICIDE in this time crop growing in effective manner is not possible because in every stage of the plant different type's weed are attacked so HERBICIDE is important for farming purpose.

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